

EFFECT OF DHATRYADI KWATHA IN MUTRAKRICHHRA

*¹Dr. Nure Azim, ²Dr. Sanjay Kumar Tripathi Sir, ³Dr. O. P. Singh Sir¹P.G. Scholar, ²Professor, ³Professor & H.O.D.

P.G. Department of Kayachikitsa, Rishikul Campus, UAU, Haridwar.

Article Received on 05 April 2026,
Article Revised on 25 April 2026,
Article Published on 01 May 2026,<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20032957>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Nure Azim

P.G. Scholar, P.G. Department of
Kayachikitsa, Rishikul Campus,
UAU, Haridwar.

How to cite this Article: ¹Dr. Nure Azim, ²Dr. Sanjay Kumar Tripathi Sir, ³Dr. O. P. Singh Sir (2026). Effect Of Dhatryadi Kwatha In Mutrakrichhra. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(9), 1440–1446.
This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Mutrakricchra is an important disease described in *Ayurveda* under *Mutravaha Srotas*(urinary system)disorders.^[1] *Mutra* is considered one among the *Trimala*. *Mutra* plays a major role in *kledavahana*. *Basti* one of the *Trimarma*, which is the *srotomoola* of the *Mutra*.^[2]

“मूत्रकृच्छ्रं दुःखेन मूत्रप्रवृत्ति”| It is mentioned as the *Pratyatma Lakshana* of *Mutrakrichhra* in *Ayurvedic* texts which means the act of urination with *Dukha* (discomfort) is called *Mutrakrichhra*. In modern medicine science, *Mutrakrichhra* can be corelated with Dysuria. One of the most common cause of dysuria is urinary tract infection(UTI) which occurs in both males and females. **The prevalence of Dysuria**, Dysuria affects apporximately 3% of all adults over the ages of 40 at any given time,making it one of the most common urinary

symptoms.^[3] *Mutrakricchra* though more frequently seen in case of females but prevalence also increases in men with increasing age.

INTRODUCTION

The word *Mutra* is derived from the term ‘*Prasrav*’ which means to ooze, and ‘*krichhra*’ is derived from the word ‘*Kastae*’ which means pain or discomfort. *Mutrakrichhra* is a common urinary disorder characterized by painful and difficult micturition. It is caused by the vitiation of doshas affecting the *Mutravaha Srotas*.

Mutrakricchra is often correlated with dysuria. **Dysuria** defined as discomfort and pain while voiding urine. It is often associated with frequency of micturition, burning and feeling of incomplete emptying of the bladder.

In *Ayurveda* broad explanation of *nidan*, *lakshan* and treatment is given by various *Acharyas*. There are so many special procedure and hundreds of medications as a successful and safer remedy for the *Mutrakricchra* disease. Line of treatment in *Ayurveda* target *Mutravaha Strotasa* and balancing the vitiated *Tridoshas*.

This article explains the role of *Dhatryadi kwatha* in treatment of *Mutrakricchra*. *Dhatryadi kwatha* contains *Dhatri*, *Draksha*, *Vidarikand*, *Yasthimadhu* and *Gokshur*.

NIDANA

व्यायामतीक्ष्णौषधरुक्षमद्यप्रसंगनित्यद्रुतपृष्ठयानात् ।

आनूपमत्स्यध्यशनादजीर्णात् स्युर्मूत्रकृच्छ्राणिनृणामिहाष्टौ ॥ (च चि26/32).^[4]

LAKSHANA

मूत्रस्य कृच्छ्रेण महता दुःखेन प्रवृत्तिः। (मधुकोष)^[5]

SAMPRAPTI CHAKRA OF MUTRAKRICCHRA^[6]

Content of Dhatryadi Kwatha^[7]

- 1] *Amalaki* (*Embllica officinalis*)
- 2] *Draksha* (*Vitis vinifera*)
- 3] *Vidarikanda* (*Pueraria tuberosa*)
- 4] *Yashtimadhu* (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*)
- 5] *Gokshura* (*Tribulus terrestris*)

Table 2: Pharmacological properties of drug.

Drug	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Dosha karma	Therapeutic uses	Pharmacological action
<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Pancha rasa Amla prdhana lavan rahit</i>	<i>Guru, Ruksha, sheeta</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Tridosha Shamaka (Visheshta pitta shamaka)</i>	<i>Mutrakrichhra, Rasayana, Shoolhara, Dahaprashmana</i>	Antibacterial, Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory
<i>Draksha</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Snigdha, Guru, Mridu</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamaka</i>	<i>Dahaprashmana, Raktpitta Shamaka, Virechnopaga, Mutral</i>	Diuretics, Laxative, Antioxidant, Antimicrobial
<i>Vidarikanda</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamaka</i>	<i>Mutral, Dahaprashmana, Anulomana.</i>	Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory
<i>Yashtimadhu</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Tridosha Shamaka</i>	<i>Dahaprashmana, Raktpitta Shamaka, Vranaropana, Rasayana</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Antimicrobial
<i>Gokshura</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Guru, Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Shamaka</i>	<i>Vednasthapana, Shothara, Shoolprashmana</i>	Diuretic, Anti-inflammatory, Anti-spasmodic, Antibacterial

AMALAKI

It Possesses *Tridosha shamaka (Visheshta pitta shamaka)*, *Rasayana*, *Dahaprashamaka*, *Mutrakrichhra* hara property.^[8]

Chemical composition- Tannin, Ascorbic acid, Ellagic acid, Gallic acid.

Pharmacological activity^[12]

- Amalaki has *Rasayana* property. It rejuvenates *Mutravaha Srotasa* (urinary system) and prevents recurrence and improves tissue strength.
- It possesses antibacterial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory property.

- Amalaki is Rich in vit. C and polyphenols. It helps combat infections that may contribute to urinary discomfort.
- Gallic acid present in Amalaki Shows activity against urinary pathogens like Escherichia coli. IT disrupts bacterial cell membranes and enzyme systems.

DRAKSHA

It Possesses *Vata-Pitta Shamaka Dahaprashmana, Raktpitta Shamaka, Mutral* property.^[9]

Chemical composition- (+) Catechin, (-) Epicatechin, Beta Sitosterol, Ergosterol.

Pharmacological activity^[12]

- *Draksha* has *Madhura Rasa* and *Sheta virya* property. So it helps pacify *Pitta Dosha*, which is mainly responsible for burning micturition.
- It possesses Diuretics, Antioxidant, Antimicrobial property.
- Catechins are natural polyphenolic antioxidant, which protect cells from damage caused by free radicals.

VIDARIKAND

It Possesses *Mutral, Dahaprashmana, Anulomana* property.^[10]

Chemical composition- Purerarin, Genistein, Daidzein, Quercetin.

Pharmacological activity^[12]

- As mentioned in *Susrut Samhita*, *Vidarikand* has diuretic property. So *Vidarikand* increases urine flow, Flushes urinary tract, and relieves obstruction.^[11]
- It possesses Diuretic, Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory property.
- Genistein inhibits pro inflammatory mediators and reduces inflammation of urinary tract mucosa, which is a key cause of pain and burning in *Mutrakrichhra*.

YASHTIMADHU

It Possesses *Tridosha Shamaka, Dahaprashmana, Rasayana, Raktpitta Shamaka, Vranaropana*.^[12]

Chemical composition- Glycyrrhizin, Glycyrrhizic acid, Liquirtin, Liquiritic acid.

Pharmacological activity^[12]

- *Yashtimadhu* is *pitta shamaka* due to *Madhura rasa* and *Sheeta virya*. It also *vata shamaka* due to *Snigdha* and *Guru guna*, So *Yashtimadhu* relieves *Daha*, *Shoola* and *Mutra kricchata*(difficulty).
- It Possesses Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Antimicrobial property.
- Glycyrrhizin inhibits inflammatory mediator(prostaglandins, cytokines)and reduces inflammation of bladder and urethral mucosa.

❖ GOKSHURA

Gokshur is described in *Mutravirechaniya Mahakashaya* and *Shotha hara Mahakashaya* by *Acharaya Charaka*.^[13]

It Possesses Vata Pitta Shamaka, Mutrala, Ashmarinashana, Vatanuta, Shotha-Hara, Krimighna, Raktapittashamaka property.^[14]

Chemical composition- Saponins (Harmine), Flavonoids, Alkaloids, Tanins.

Pharmacological activity^[12]

- It possesses anti- inflammatory, anti- bacterial, anti-urolithic, diuretic, antioxidant, analgesic property.
- Diuretic activity of *Gokshur* is due to presence of high concentration of potassium salts, nitrates and essential oils present in fruits and seeds.
- Methanolic extract of fruits of *Gokshur* found effective against gram positive and gram negative bacteria.

SHARKARA- *Sharkara* is derivative of *ikshu*.

- It is used as a Anupana of *Dhatryadi kwatha*
- It possesses Anti-inflammatory, Diuretic property.
- It is mentioned in *Susrut Samhita Balya, Vrashya, Mutrala* and *Raktapittashamak*.^[15]

DISCUSSION

Dhatryadi kwatha Shows *Tridosha-Shamaka, Mutrala, Anulomaka, Daha-shamaka, Rakta pitta shamaka, shoolhara* properties based on the pharmacological attributes(Dravya-guna) of its constituent drugs described earlier. It acts on *Mutravaha srotas* to relieve *Mutrakricchra*. On modern parameters these drugs can be understood to anti inflammatory, anti oxidant, anti microbial, anti spasmodic. diuretic and mild laxative actions.

Probable mode of action on Samprapti Vighatan

<i>Samprapti ghataka</i>	<i>Mutrakrichhra</i>	<i>Treatment</i>
<i>Dosha</i>	<i>Tridosha(Vata pradhan)</i>	<i>Tridoshaghna</i>
<i>Dushya</i>	<i>Mutra</i>	<i>Mutrala</i>
<i>Agni</i>	<i>Agnimandya</i>	<i>Deepana, pachana</i>
<i>Srotas</i>	<i>Mutravahasrotasa</i>	<i>Mutrala</i>
<i>Adhishtana</i>	<i>Basti and mutravahasrotasa</i>	<i>Mutrala</i>
<i>Dushtiprakarana</i>	<i>Sanga</i>	<i>Chedana, bhedana, lekhana</i>

CONCLUSION

Mutrakricchra is described by various *Acharyas* in *Ayurvedic texts*. *Mutrakricchra* can be present in form of independent disease as well as *Lakshana* of other diseases. The modern science has no specific medicaments for cure of Dysuria but symptomatic treatment like antibiotic are used, the uses of antibiotics has resolved the problem but relapses, resistance and side effects are also associated with their long term use. There are numbers of preparations described in *Ayurvedic text* and *Dhatryadi kwatha* is one among them. It has effective properties that helps in curing *Mutrakricchra*, provide safe and cost effective treatment in *Ayurveda*.

REFERENCES

1. Madhav Nidan with Madhukosh Sanskrit Commentary by Shri Vijayraksita & Shri Kanthadatta with Vidyotini Hindi Commentary revised & edited by Prof. Yadunandan Upadhyaya, Part-1, Chaukhambha Prakashan, Varanasi Mutrakrichhra nidana adhyaya, 30.
2. Sapre, S.D., Babar, S.C., & Jondhale, P.B.(2020). Efficacy Of Trinapanchmoola Kwatha In The Management Of Pittaja Mutrakrichhra. Paripax Indian J Res, 9(11): 96-97.
3. <https://www.aafp.org> Article Dysuria:Evaluation and Differential Diagnosis in Adults abstract Data taken from introduction on date, 9 march 2020.
4. Charaka Samhita Vidyotni Hindi Commentary, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy, Varansi, Reprint year, 2013; Vol-1.
5. Madhav Nidan with Madhukosh Sanskrit Commentary, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy, Varansi.
6. Negi Bhavya: To study the Effect of Gokshur in Mutrakricchra of Pregnancy 2019, Rishikul Campus Haridwar.
7. Bhaishajya Ratnawali, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy, Varansi, Mutrakrichhra Adhyaya.
8. Dravya Guna Vigyan, Acharya Priyavrat Sharma, Vol II, Chaukhambha Bharti

- Academy Reprint, 2011.
9. Dravya Guna Vigyan, Acharya Priyavrat Sharma, Vol II, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy Reprint, 2011.
 10. Dravya Guna Vigyan, Acharya Priyavrat Sharma, Vol II, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy Reprint, 2011.
 11. Sushruta Samhita Ayurvedatvasandeeepika Hindi Commentary by Dr. Ambika Dutt Shastri, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy, Varansi Vol 1.
 12. Dravya Guna Vigyan, Acharya Priyavrat Sharma, Vol II, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy Reprint, 2011.
 13. Charaka Samhita Vidyotni Hindi Commentary, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy, Varansi, Reprint year, 2013; 1.
 14. Dravya Guna Vigyan, Acharya Priyavrat Sharma, Vol II, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy Reprint, 2011.
 15. Sushruta Samhita Ayurvedatvasandeeepika Hindi Commentary by Dr. Ambika Dutt Shastri, Chaukhambha Bharti Academy, Varansi Vol 1.